

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Project Data Management Plan (v.2)

Deliverable D7.2

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List of Acronyms

AABW	Antarctic bottom water
AANCHOR	All Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation
AAPP	Australian Antarctic Program Partnership
ACC	Antarctic Circumpolar Current
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AIS	Antarctic Ice Sheet
AMOC	Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
ApRES	Autonomous Phase-sensitive Radio Echo Sounder
AUV	Autonomous underwater vehicle
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum Für Polar- Und Meeresforschung
AWS	Automatic weather stations
BSH	Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring System
CNRS	Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique
CNRS-IGE	Centre national de la recherche scientifique - Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement
DACs	Data archive centres
DATAMEQ	Data Management, Exchange and Quality Working Group
DFFE	Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
DU	Dissemination Unit
ECMWF	European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDMERP	European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Projects
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
EF	Environmental Monitoring Facilities
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPCO	European Polar Coordination Office
ESA	European Space Agency
ESMs	Earth System Model
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, re-usable
FESOM	Finite-Element/volumE Sea ice-Ocean Model
FOSS	Free and open-source software
GCM	Generic Conceptual Model
GNOS	GeoNetwork open-source
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
INS	In situ
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITGC	International Thwaites Glacier Collaboration

JARE	Japanese Antarctic Research Expedition
JRC	Joint Research Centre
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NMO	Numerical models
NORCE	Norwegian Research Centre
NorESM	Norwegian Earth System Model
NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OBP	Ocean best practices
OCG	Observation Coordination Group
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OF	Oceanographic Geographical Features
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
PISM-MOM	Parallel Ice Sheet Model-Modular Ocean Model
RCM	Real climate model
SAMBA	South Atlantic MOC Basin-wide Array
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Network
SEANOE	Sea Open Scientific Data Publication
SLR	Sea level rise
SMB	Surface mass balance
SMOS	Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity
SR	Sea Regions
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SSP	Shared socio-economic pathway
TICs	Turbulence instrument clusters
TipMip	TIPping point Model Intercomparison Project
UGOT	University of Gothenburg
UKESM	The UK Earth System Modelling project
UKRI-BAS	United Kingdom Research and Innovation - British Antarctic Survey
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNIVBRIS	University of Bristol
UNN	University of Northumbria at Newcastle
UoS	University of Southampton
UREAD	University of Reading
VM	Virtual machine
WAF	Web Accessible Folder
WOA	World Ocean Assessment
WP	Work package

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1 Publishable summary

OCEAN:ICE provides products to both internal and external users. The data workflow is based on a chain of individual operational components, each contributing either to data production or user interaction functions. The infrastructure implements open and free of charge data access, it adopts international standards, follows European regulations such as INSPIRE, it is accessible under the OCEAN:ICE web domain (www.ocean-ice.eu) and offers up to date means of data and data products dissemination and interaction tools.

Nevertheless, the developed system cannot be considered finally closed, and for the entire duration of the project, the following evolution principles have to be considered and applied:

- **The service shall be state-of-the-art in its scope, and it shall be user-driven.**

This means that all service capabilities are defined, allocated and implemented with sound and state-of-the-art technical and scientific justifications and address OCEAN:ICE internal and external user needs. If new needs pop up, it is important to try and match (whenever possible) these new needs. Providing international level state-of-the-art tools means a constant monitoring and application of most appropriate methodologies at a given time to meet requirements for service quality in data processing, validation, etc.

- **Common standards are adopted and applied throughout the different elements of the system.**

This means that standards are identified, adopted and applied. If, during the lifetime of the project, rising ocean best practices (OBP) become standards, the project has to try and include (as much as possible) these new OBP.

This also means that the system evolves constantly in response to service requirements, scientific and technical requirements, marine environment products requirements, stakeholders' requirements.

- **Quality of the methodology of workflow has to follow and apply, well-established engineering methodologies derived from industry (e.g., ISO9001:2015, ISO15288, etc.) drive the definition of an adapted approach.**

This means that data management also adopts good practices and methodologies to ensure system monitoring, fixing and reporting.

Within this framework, OCEAN:ICE poses itself amongst the up-to-date data infrastructure projects, adopts the latest interoperability best practices and enables data-products FAIRness to maximise the OCEAN:ICE data value chain from production to its end use for added value ocean products.

DMP is a living document, and this deliverable presents the updated version of OCEAN:ICE DMP. To facilitate the reader to see latest assumptions, the updates are highlighted in yellow.

2 Scope of the document

This document presents the updated version of the OCEAN:ICE Data Management Plan (DMP). It extends the preliminary version of the OCEAN:ICE DMP (D7.1) that is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) template. OCEAN:ICE moves beyond open access in implementing open science practices while following Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles. It applies to research data collected during the project as well as to publications.

All observational data (i.e. in situ data) and derived products will be made freely available via EU public data repositories and/or international TRUST repositories (e.g. SOOS). As planned, OCEAN:ICE data management (WP7) uses tools that organize data in the OCEAN:ICE backend system that provides immediate and free access to collected data. Besides adopting open data management software tools (e.g. ERDDAP, GeoServer, GeoNetwork), and supporting INSPIRE themes (e.g. European harmonised and controlled vocabularies), OCEAN:ICE started contributing to the development of needed extensions. As soon as they are ready for, these will be shared via open repositories (e.g. GitHub, StackOverflow) as well as provide docker images of deployed and configured tools. Project developed data management software tools are made freely available under creative commons/open data commons licencing. As a first example, WP7 is developing an educational page to present how to use OCEAN:ICE data to develop ocean products (<https://literacy.s4oceanice.eu/intro.html>) which code is made publicly available in GitHub (<https://github.com/s4oceanice/literacy.s4oceanice>)

The document recalls the scope of the OCEAN:ICE project and describe the OCEAN:ICE framework for the research data management according the requirements of Article 17 of the Grant Agreement. These include description of data (data summary), approach to FAIRness, research outputs, allocation of resources, security and ethics.

Document Disclaimers:

This document is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template [V1.1 April 2022] and adapted to provide the OCEAN:ICE partners and OCEAN:ICE stakeholders a living guide for the project Data Management Plan. The Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of the content of this publication.

3 Data summary

Timely, free and unrestricted exchange of oceanographic observational data is essential for understanding the oceans' complex role in the weather and the climate, for empowering decision makers with evidence-based information for sustainable management of the ocean and environment. Open and free data policy is widely encouraged by the European Commission and Member States for a wide range of environmental data services targeted to a wide range of user communities. Interoperability of data systems has become a priority with the development of FAIR principles (2014) (<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>), a set of guiding principles (2016) to make data **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable**.

Furthermore, in 2021, OECD, with the Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data, set principles and policy guidance to help governments to maximise the cross-sectoral benefits of all types of data – personal, non-personal, open, proprietary, public and private – while protecting the rights of individuals and organizations.

The availability and accessibility of these data is not always easy and often the sources are lacking compliance to international standards, and many challenges (still) exist associated with good management of ocean data, such as using different formats, wide diversity of datasets, and disparate data management structures, among others (Tanhua et al., 2019). Anyhow, the basic milestones are set and can be easily adopted and adapted to the purpose. This comprises, open science practices covering the entire workflow of the ocean data production and dissemination, including data processing, validation and dissemination infrastructure(s).

3.1 Purpose of data generation/reuse

The objective of OCEAN:ICE is to assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes studying their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate. OCEAN:ICE uses a combination of old and new observations and numerical models.

OCEAN:ICE is planning a set of quasi-simultaneous circumpolar observations over periods of several years [2022-2024]. Old and new data are both in situ and remote sensing observations. New observations **are** addressed in circumpolar and Atlantic areas to reduce currents gaps. These observations **are** used to feed models and produce new estimates of (the giant) ice sheet melt and impacts on ocean circulation (including the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation – AMOC), global sea level rise and other critical climate parameters over the coming decades and centuries. OCEAN:ICE uses already available coupled ice sheet-climate models and develops/advances these models.

The figure shows the OCEAN:ICE structure and addressed goals:

Figure 1. OCEAN:ICE structure and addressed goals (April 2024)

Where WP1-WP6, WP10 and WP11 are the data and products generators. Each WP is organized in tasks and each task is either producing, assessing or developing a data/product:

Figure 2. Pert Chart (April 2024).

The figure indicates the fundamental process studies in WP1, WP2, WP3, **WP10-WP11**. These studies support model construction and analysis (WP4- 6) and the structured nature of the model experimental design.

3.2 Novel data and re-use of data

As anticipated in the previous section, OCEAN:ICE is organized in WPs and tasks, each (WP1-WP6) task is consuming or producing data products being in one of these three main categories:

- 1) in situ (INS) observational data (including reanalysis and virtual in situ observational sites)
- 2) satellite derived Earth Observational (EO) products
- 3) numerical models (NMO)

Table 1. Summary of categories of data products for each OCEAN:ICE work package.

	INS	EO	NMO
WP1	X	X	X
WP2	X		X
WP3	X	X	X
WP4			X
WP5	X		X
WP6			X
WP10	X		X
WP11	X	X	X

In WP1, “Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export”, and in WP10, “Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export”, OCEAN:ICE targets address the key processes, connectivity and circulation of the Antarctic shelf seas. More specifically OCEAN:ICE proposes an ambitious circumpolar programme of instrument deployments, including mooring and novel profiling float arrays over the continental shelf.

WP1 will assess:

- Dynamic Processes:
 - a) Aggregate existing and complement circumpolar mooring records;
 - b) Gathering sea ice formation time series complemented with historical shipboard surveys and numerical model experiments (1979-present hindcast);
 - c) Analyse tides and eddy kinetic energy on Antarctic shelf seas;
 - d) Assess energy propagation from one shelf sea to another with continental shelf waves based on new virtual and regular mooring observations;
 - e) Assess shelf waves, dynamics and local thermodynamics with satellite-based SSH records and sea ice formation time series.
- Advective processes linking and impacting adjacent shelf seas:
 - a) Novel float deployments;
 - b) Prepare and evaluate a 1979-present FESOM model hindcast with data from novel float deployments in sparsely observed regions;
 - c) Assess circumpolar connectivity through the coastal current and along-slope circulation via zonal fluxes of energy and freshwater across flux gates between adjacent shelf seas.
- The Southern Ocean as a heat source for glacial melt:
 - a) On continental slope front processes regulating the transfer of ocean heat to the ice shelf;
 - b) Quantification of shelf edge fluxes leading to the observed ocean heat content variability in the Amundsen/Bellingshausen-sector.
- Shelf Seas as a dense water source for the global thermohaline circulation:
 - a) FESOM hindcast will be used to investigate dense water formation, variability and pathways in the Ross and Weddell Seas;
 - b) Formation on seasonal to interannual time scales, complemented with long-term ocean records and tracer-based water mass age and melt water fractions;
 - c) Deployment of new oceanographic moorings to identify trends and variabilities in the bottom water outflows.

WP10 will assess:

- The hydrological structure of the marine environment waters of the Northwest Weddell Sea:
 - a) Deploy profiling floats and mooring equipment to monitor water mass transportation pathways;
 - b) Calibrate purchased equipment for observation locations.

OCEAN:ICE members and partners make available and consume data from existing mooring arrays in the Amundsen Sea (UKRI-BAS), eastern (KOPRI) and western Ross Sea (NIWA).

The new sensors and platforms from OCEAN:ICE are:

- Floats and ice-capable floats,
- AUV missions,
- Ship-based transects,
- cavity turbulence (UKRI-BAS) and oxygen isotopes measurements,
- continuous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ water isotope ratios,
- turbulence instrument clusters,
- cavity hydrography and helium isotopes observations,
- AABW salinity and transport variability monitoring, by adding sensors in SAMBA array.

These sensors and platforms are largely expanding the monitoring capacity in the Southern Oceans and enabling the development of several derived data collections and products by aggregating and complementing with (the reuse of) current, hydrographic and bottom pressure sensors from historical regular mooring observations (led by AWI, UKRI-BAS, CNRS, NPI and NORCE) and new virtual data upstream, in front of and under the Filchner ice shelf, thereby covering the other key sector of abyssal water formation and variability¹.

Recent studies demonstrate the viability of shelf sea float deployments where seabed parking between casts is used to minimize drift and allow float operation as full-depth virtual moorings, even in ice-covered regions². More specifically, WP1 will deploy three pairs of ice-capable floats in regions that are currently poorly observed and represent important links between regions of significant ice-ocean interaction.

One pair will be deployed between the Amundsen and the Ross Sea (KOPRI supported), to connect upstream and downstream moored arrays and the other two pairs along the East Antarctic margin near the Denman Glacier (AAPP/GEOMAR), and Totten Ice Shelf (JARE).

The resulting time series ensemble, coherently covering at least the 2020-2024 time period (and 2009-present in the Amundsen Sea).

WP1 uses satellite-based SSH to assess Shelf waves, dynamics and local thermodynamics propagation and sea ice formation time series. WP1 will use numerical model experiments (1979-present hindcast), complemented with data from novel float deployments in sparsely observed regions; and assesses circumpolar connectivity through the coastal current and along-slope circulation via zonal fluxes of energy and freshwater across flux gates between adjacent shelf seas, Agreements with national float deployment programs (e.g. German ARGO programme), past success by project members in acquiring floats through national float procurement programmes (e.g. CNRS)

¹ Naughten et al. (2021) - <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22259-0>

² Wallace et al. (2020) - [10.1029/2020GL087019](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL087019)

and partner co-deployments and data sharing arrangements (e.g. partners AAPP) are anticipated to significantly enhance the OCEAN:ICE owned array to ~20 floats, including CNRS obtained deep (>4000m) ARGO floats. Additional float pairs will be deployed near moorings for intercomparison/calibration, in additional locations along East Antarctica (the greatest data gap), and west of Fimbul ice shelf to track signals as they propagate towards the Filchner-Ronne. Expected deep floats will be deployed in the outflow regions from the Ross (Cape Adare) and the Weddell Seas to observe AABW pathways

FESOM hindcast will be used to investigate dense water formation on seasonal to interannual time scales, complemented with long-term ocean records and tracer-based water mass age and melt water fractions. Identify trends and variabilities in the bottom water outflows using new oceanographic moorings and establish or refute connections with multidecadal freshening trends.

WP10 will deploy profiling floats and mooring equipment to monitor water mass transportation pathways from NASC research vessel Noosfera during the Antarctic seasons 2024-2025 and 2025-2026. In addition, WP10 will share best practices in operating instrumentation, post-processing of data and research skills. Training and knowledge exchange will be organized at AWI, BAS and on Noosfera on: operation of oceanographic instrumentation; post-processing and analysis of data; science focus on thermohaline structure of regional water masses, transformation of shelf water, formation of the frontal zone in the Bransfield Strait.

In WP2, “Cryosphere-ocean interaction, processes and feedbacks”, OCEAN:ICE focuses on the key role that ice sheet-ocean interaction plays in melting ice shelves and the export and freshwater distribution of icebergs. WP2 targets to:

- Improved representation of icebergs in ESMs:
 - a) Develop and improve the iceberg module in NEMO;
 - b) Assessed in regional and global simulations to investigate the model recreation of observed Bear Ridge icebergs and attached sea ice and increased iceberg discharge at regional to global scales.
- Observing the ocean beneath the sea ice fasten to grounded icebergs:
 - a) Several 24h missions of the UGOT-AUV to explore the Bear Ridge area.
- Observing the ocean near and within ice-shelf cavities:
 - a) Ship-based transects and the AUV near and under the front of Thwaites or Dotson ice shelf measuring the exchange of properties and ice draft and bathymetry;
 - b) Incorporates UGOT historical data from the ITGC project 2019-2022.
- Observing the ice-shelf/ocean interface of a cold cavity:
 - a) Deploy instrumentation to measuring cavity turbulence (UKRI-BAS) and oxygen isotopes (CNRS-IGE) on Fimbul ice shelf via NPI boreholes and logistics.
- Using water isotopes to better tune and evaluate ocean models:
 - a) Develop NEMO capacity to represent ice-shelf melt water isotopes;
 - b) Tested in regional model configuration constrained by global surface isotopic concentrations.

WP2 develops and improves the iceberg module in NEMO, improve NEMO capacity to represent ice-shelf melt water isotopes, and delivers novel observations of the processes controlling ice sheet-ocean interactions under and immediately around warm (Amundsen Sea region) and cold (Fimbul) ice shelves.

Cool ice shelf observations will be made through boreholes on the Fimbul Ice Shelf (2023/24 season), supported by project members NPI³. Two OCEAN:ICE instruments will be deployed within the ice shelf cavity. Firstly, a novel instrument developed at CNRS providing continuous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ water isotope ratios will be deployed in the Antarctic for the first time. This will provide a new method of determining mixing, melt and refreezing across the ocean boundary layer beneath the ice shelf, expanding recent applications of this novel tracer within the region⁴. Secondly, three UKRI-BAS turbulence instrument clusters (TICs) will be deployed across a basal channel: one at the channel center, one on the channel flank, and one outside the channel extent. This yearlong deployment will measure basal melt rates and resolve the turbulent scalar and momentum fluxes in the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer responsible for driving basal melting. OCEAN:ICE observations will be complimented by contemporaneous NPI observations of the cavity hydrography and helium isotopes. Together these observations will elucidate the mixing and turbulent dynamics of the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer and impacts on basal melting; key to the development of next-generation melt rate parameterizations and model tracer representation.

A Hugin autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) operated by UGOT (deployed by KOPRI, 2022/23 season) will be used to acquire new hydrographic and bathymetric data from the ice shelf cavities of Thwaites, Dotson, and/or Pine Island Glaciers, as well as the iceberg 'graveyard' on Bear Ridge. This builds on previous successful missions to the area⁵ and focuses on the region near the calving front, where dynamical constraints are active and pose limitations for the warm water inflow⁶ in addition to the active water mass mixing and modification which take place here.¹⁶

Few hydrographic transects have been performed near the ice shelf fronts and even fewer in the high-risk areas where icebergs are stranded in large numbers, such as Bear Ridge. There are still large areas where the bathymetry is poorly known, including the important ice shelf cavities⁷. OCEAN:ICE is going run to Ship-based transects and the AUV near and under the front of Thwaites or Dotson ice shelf.

These novel observations made under and around grounded icebergs and surrounding sea-ice on Bear Ridge will provide otherwise unobtainable in situ data for the tuning and validation of iceberg module development within NEMO and deploy in coupled ice sheet-climate modelling.

WP2 will also deploy instrumentation to measuring cavity turbulence (UKRI-BAS) and oxygen isotopes (CNRS-IGE) on Fimbul ice shelf.

In WP3, “Ice sheet mass balance, forcing and dynamics”, and in WP11, “Atmosphere and ocean dynamics”, OCEAN:ICE will provide updated values and uncertainties for freshwater fluxes from the AIS to the ocean over the satellite observational period to the present day, including surface melt and runoff, ice flow, basal melt and calving. Moreover, OCEAN:ICE will quantify freshwater flux from solid and liquid precipitation in the Antarctic peninsula, assess the ocean circulation beneath ice shelves in the Weddell Sea and the impact of breaking waves on ice melt rates.

WP3 will include the following:

- EO: contribution of continental scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes.
 - a) Produce a comprehensive EO dataset of AIS freshwater fluxes, including calving fluxes, basal melt (ApRES) and EO surface melt rates.

³ Hattermann et al. (2020) - <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL051012>

⁴ Akhoudas et al. (2020) - <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015710>

⁵ England et al. (2020) - DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abd1273

⁶ Wählin et al. (2020) - <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2014-5>

⁷ Jenkins et al. (2010) - <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo890>

- Contribution of surface mass budget and ice shelf processes:
 - a) Produce RCM surface fluxes accounting for wind blown snow, firn densification and saturation and basal ice shelf melt;
 - b) Assimilation of SMB and basal melt into a hindcast covering the whole AIS to initialise ice sheet models and identify atmospheric variability impacts on ice sheet mass budget.
- Subglacial fresh-water discharge from the AIS into the Southern Ocean:
 - a) Compute buoyancy plume driven melt and subglacial discharge contribution to ice shelves computed using state-of-the art surface-to-bed inversions and a subglacial hydrological model to provide the first estimates of water fluxes across all grounding lines on a continental wide basis.
- Developing methodologies for hindcasting from ice-sheet models:
 - a) Using a regional coupled model and applying the IEnKS initialization algorithm for initialising coupled ice-ocean models, idealised domains and synthetic observations will be used to provide a proof of concept, and a realistic regional Amundsen Sea initialisation;
 - b) Apply ensemble-based assimilation to choose initial state and parameters of ice sheet-ocean model minimising mismatch and drift.

WP11 will include the following:

- **Historical evaluation:**
 - a) Assess the importance of rain and snow precipitation in the Southern Ocean and the occurrence of extreme events over the Antarctic Peninsula region using high-resolution climate downscaling.
- **Particle tracking:**
 - a) Modelling of Weddell Sea circulation using particle tracking to determine float placement pre-fieldwork and to analyze and verify model simulations with float data;
 - b) Assessment of the importance of internal waves on ice melt rates.
- **PolarWRF Modelling:**
 - a) High-resolution PolarWRF simulations (9-3-1km) with two-moment microphysics parameterizations to compare with the observations of precipitation during extreme events.

WP3 produces a comprehensive EO dataset of AIS freshwater fluxes, including calving fluxes, basal melt (ApRES) and EO surface melt rates. Existing ApRES (in situ phase-sensitive radar time series of ice shelf thickness at ~1 mm precision) datasets will be consolidated and integrated with other open AWS observational datasets, shallow ice cores and snow stake measurements into a comprehensive model evaluation dataset. ApRES observations will also be used as independent evaluation of snowfall accumulation rates from RCMs and satellite derived basal melt rates over ice shelves. These are sensitive to model physics in RCM and are some of the largest uncertainties currently associated with mass budget estimates in Antarctica. WP3 uses state-of-the art models while the above approach represents a significant community advance for assessing model uncertainties.

In WP4, “Quantification of Antarctic Ice Sheet ‘deep uncertainty’, OCEAN:ICE utilises improved initialisation states from WP3 to project the freshwater fluxes of the AIS in ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-ocean models from 2020-2300 and its contribution to SLR. More specifically it does:

- Model initialization and initial sensitivity analysis.

- a) Apply optimization techniques and data on bedrock elevation, ice thickness, ice thickness changes, surface velocity, surface mass balance and ice shelf basal to estimate the present-day state of the AIS employing the f.ETISH model (ULB) and the Úa model (UNN).
- b) Assess the spread in AIS fluxes for a range of uncertain glaciological processes.
- Surrogate modelling and UQ in Antarctic ice sheet models.
 - a) A large ensemble of 300-year long simulations will be carried out with f.ETISH and Úa, each covering the full space of uncertain physical parameters and uncertain climate forcing.
 - b) train multi-output surrogate models for calving, basal melt, surface runoff and the grounding line fluxes. Stochastic analysis of model uncertainties and a full sensitivity analysis for all Antarctic drainage basins.
- Benchmarking against high-resolution coupled ice-ocean simulations.
 - a) High-resolution simulations of the coupled ÚaMITgcm for Amundsen and Weddell Sea drainage basins. 300-year simulations for an ‘optimal’ range of model parameters and forcings, to capture AIS sensitivity.
 - b) Further develop ÚaMITgcm configurations to include moving ice fronts and surface runoff. Coupled ice-ocean response compared to ice sheet only simulations, and feedbacks analysed.

In WP5, “Ice sheet impacts on global ocean circulation”, OCEAN:ICE examines the impact of ice sheet meltwater discharge on deep water formation and export from the poles, and the ultimate impact upon large scale ocean circulation, including the AMOC and ACC. More specifically, it considers:

- Bottom water transport and properties:
 - a) Installation of an AABW physics monitoring mooring array in the South Sandwich Trench.
 - b) It will make the first sustained mooring observation of the primary AABW pathway from the Weddell Sea to the global ocean.
 - c) Determine AABW transport, properties and variability, linked to contemporaneous mooring observations in Orkney Passage and elsewhere in the Weddell Sea, EO and reanalysis wind data, model output.
 - d) Supplement the SAMBA array with AABW monitoring instrumentation.
 - e) Examine the AABW salinity and transport variability in the context of upstream water mass properties, freshwater inputs and SAMBA.
 - f) AABW contribution to AMOC via new instruments deployments in the SAMBA array
- North-South freshwater impacts on ocean circulation up to millennial timescales.
 - a) Global hydrographic data, including water isotopes, inversion to reconstruct surface boundary conditions on decadal to (multi) centennial timescales.
 - b) Reconstruction of surface oxygen isotope ratios, and meteoric water/sea-ice impact on dense water properties.
 - c) NEMO simulations up to 3,000 years forced with increased ice mass loss in Antarctica and Greenland scenarios. NorESM (coupled Greenland ice sheet) decadal IPCC-SSP climate scenario simulations. Both simulations assess the impact of increased glacial melting on global ocean circulation, including impacts on the AMOC, ACC and upper-ocean gyres and southern and northern deep-water formation.

An array of three moorings (provided by UKRI-BAS, logistics by South African DFFE) will be deployed across the unobserved main AABW flow path from the Weddell Sea, across the ridge crossing the southern part of the South Sandwich Trench, measuring temperature, salinity, pressure and velocity. A two-year deployment will allow the first estimates of total Weddell Sea AABW export properties and variability. This will be concurrent with the existing UKRI-BAS Orkney Passage array, the other primary AABW pathway, enabling direct comparisons of magnitude and co-variability, and potential reconstruction of past export.

To link this work to the global circulation and understand the basin scale impact of AABW heat and freshwater content change⁸ OCEAN:ICE will establish the first continuous cross-basin monitoring of AABW properties in the South Atlantic. The deeper layer of the SAMBA array will be equipped with new sensors by SAMOC partners. Microcats measuring temperature, salinity and pressure will be added to each of eight existing ENS-LMD partnered moorings (by Brazil and South Africa SAMOC partners in 2023/2025). They will allow the first high temporal resolution observations of AABW properties across the South Atlantic.

WP5 will also provide global context for the impact of high latitude deep water formation on global ocean properties and circulation. It will use the interior distribution of water mass properties derived from existent global salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ hydrography to make a novel application of an inverse approach⁹. This will reconstruct surface boundary conditions on decadal timescales and, for older deep waters, extend the relevant surface boundary condition to (multi) centennial timescales.

This study will include an analysis of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ decorrelation length and time scales and will provide information that can be used to inform (e.g. via SOOS) new high latitude $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ sampling strategies.

The inverse analysis itself will produce a unique observation-based historical time series of surface oxygen isotope ratios. This will inform WP2 isotope modelling and can be used to inform the magnitude and likely range of variability in boundary conditions, in addition to identifying historical variability and extreme events.

In WP6, “Role of Antarctica in the global climate (long-term impacts of short-term decision-making)”, OCEAN:ICE will quantify the impact of changes in the freshwater fluxes, including icebergs, from Antarctica on the global climate system.

- Freshwater and iceberg fluxes forcing the global ocean
 - a) determine the fate and local impacts future fluxes of icebergs and freshwater leaving the Antarctic ice sheet.
 - b) Coupled Southern Ocean NEMO BISICLES simulations of the recent past will be used to validate the iceberg circulation model and freshwater input by historical ice sheet.
 - c) Projections up to 2300 will examine the impact of freshwater fluxes on large scale ocean circulation. Freshwater feedbacks onto the coupled ice sheet evolution will be emphasised and higher resolution compliments Task 6.2 (D6.1).
- Earth system impacts to 2300.
 - a) Assess the global impacts and feedbacks of enhanced polar freshwater and iceberg calving (WP2) on future climate using the UKESM coupled with interactive Greenland and Antarctica ice sheets.

⁸ Purkey and Johnson (2010) - <https://doi.org/10.1175/2010JCLI3682>.

- b) Simulations up to 2300 using the extended socio-economic pathways (SSP) and including scenarios developed in WP4 covering the full range of high-end uncertainties.
- c) An assessment of the impacts of enhanced freshwater and iceberg calving on a range of global and regional climate indices (Section 1.2.4.3) and impact on global tipping points (D6.2).
- Millennial-scale impacts and potential for tipping cascades.
 - a) Centennial runs forced by RCM output and millennial scale coupled PISM-MOM will be used to assess the risk of crossing critical thresholds in atmospheric and oceanic drivers of the ice-sheet dynamics and (rate of) ice loss (Section 1.2.4.3) (D6.3). Model development and analysis contributes to TIP-MIP planning.

3.3 Data types and data formats

As anticipated OCEAN:ICE is planning an ambitious set of quasi-simultaneous circumpolar observations to observe the pathways, properties and high-resolution variability of water masses associated with Antarctic ice-ocean interaction over periods of several years.

Figure 3. In situ methodology

Figure 4. In situ and OCEAN:ICE activities

These in situ observations include mostly delayed mode data and some operational data. OCEAN:ICE members and partners operate existing mooring arrays in the Amundsen Sea (UKRI-BAS), eastern (KOPRI) and western Ross Sea (NIWA). These data will be complemented with current, hydrographic and bottom pressure sensors to allow intercomparison between various datasets and identify propagating signals. The ensemble will provide a circumpolar waves time series covering 2020-2024 time period (and 2009-present in the Amundsen Sea). Upstream fluxes, in front of and under the Filchner ice shelf, will be reconstructed from moored time series combined with virtual moorings (where data is lacking).

Figure 5. New planned in situ observation (2023/2024) - O:I is OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE will deploy three pairs of ice-capable floats in regions that are currently poorly observed and represent important links between regions of significant ice-ocean interaction. One pair will be deployed between the Amundsen and the Ross Sea (KOPRI supported), to connect upstream and downstream moored arrays and the other two pairs along the East Antarctic margin near the Denman Glacier (AAPP/GEOMAR), and Totten Ice Shelf (JARE).

A Hugin autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) operated by UGOT (deployed by KOPRI, 2022/23 season) will be used to *acquire new hydrographic and bathymetric data from the ice shelf cavities of Thwaites, Dotson, and/or Pine Island Glaciers, as well as the iceberg 'graveyard' on Bear Ridge.*

Figure 6. AUV missions to collect Highresolution (1 dm) maps of icebase, highresolution (<5 dm) maps of seabed, T, S and O2, CO2, nitrate, FI, turbidity, watersamples(150 ml each), and current velocity

Figure 7. UAV mission (from top)

Cool ice shelf observations will be made through boreholes on the Fimbul Ice Shelf (2023/24 season). Two OCEAN:ICE instruments will be deployed within the ice shelf cavity.

Figure 8. Fimbul Ice Shelf Observatory

Firstly, a novel instrument developed at CNRS providing continuous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ water isotope ratios will be deployed in the Antarctic for the first time. This will provide a new method of determining mixing, melt and refreezing across the ocean boundary layer beneath the ice shelf, expanding recent applications of this novel tracer within the region. Secondly, three UKRI-BAS turbulence instrument clusters (TICs) will be deployed across a basal channel: one at the channel centre, one on the channel flank, and one outside the channel extent. This yearlong deployment will measure basal melt rates and resolve the turbulent scalar and momentum fluxes in the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer responsible for driving basal melting.

OCEAN:ICE observations will be complimented by contemporaneous NPI observations of the cavity hydrography and helium isotopes. Together these observations will elucidate the mixing and turbulent dynamics of the ice shelf-ocean boundary layer and impacts on basal melting.

An array of four moorings (three already provided by UKRI-BAS, logistics by South African DFFE) will be deployed across the unobserved main AABW flow path from the Weddell Sea, immediately south of the South Sandwich Trench, measuring temperature, salinity, pressure and velocity.

South Atlantic MOC Basin-wide Array (SAMBA)

Orkney Passage & South Sandwich Trench

Figure 9. AABW properties. [2022/2023] Cruise DY158: Krill work near South Georgia, A23 section repeat, M2 mooring recovery and turnaround, circuit of A76-A icesberg, 6 mooring recovered + 4 redeployed; RRS Sir David Attenborough: M3 mooring recovery and redeployment. [2023/2024 plan] working with fishing company instead of SA Agulhas II. [2024/2025 plan] Mooring cruise to Orkney Passage/M2/M3 on RRS Sir David Attenborough through BIPOLE

OCEAN:ICE is establishing the first continuous cross-basin monitoring of AABW properties in the South Atlantic by instrumenting the deepest layer of the existing SAMBA array, across the Atlantic at 34.5°S . Microcats measuring temperature, salinity and pressure will be added to each of eight existing ENS-LMD partnered moorings (by Brazil and South Africa SAMOC partners in 2023/2025).

Two automatic weather stations (AWS) will be operated on Larsen C ice shelf (UU). In addition, existing ApRES (in situ phase-sensitive radar time series of ice shelf thickness at ~ 1 mm precision) datasets will be consolidated and integrated with other open AWS observational datasets, shallow ice cores and snow stake measurements into a comprehensive model evaluation dataset.

These in situ data will be complemented with remote sensing/satellite data from major European Earth Observation programs and agencies (e.g. Copernicus, ICESat-2, SMOS, ESA, etc.)

3.4 Data utility outside the project

OCEAN:ICE's goals necessitate explicit scientific and logistical collaboration with numerous national and international research bodies. SCAR, SOOS, IASC, APECS, SIOS, is a high level, not exhaustive list of these bodies. In turn all these bodies will benefit from the OCEAN:ICE activities and outcomes.

OCEAN:ICE directly combines and dramatically extends the expertise, development and findings of three existing H2020 programmes and EU Polar Cluster Members: PROTECT (G. Durand), TiPACCs (P. Langebroek/S. Østerhus) and SO-CHIC (J.-B. Sallee). These projects respectively look at cryosphere contributions to SLR, AIS stability and the role of the Southern Ocean in global climate. OCEAN:ICE combines these foci into a coherent view of the role of AIS freshwater flux within the global climate and includes the coordinators, numerous WP leads and other members of these projects. OCEAN:ICE has been carefully constructed to compliment, combine and extend these projects. It also links with PolarRES (R. Mottram) and output from PolarRES will supplement WP3 with regional climate simulations for both present and future scenarios. Additionally, it will benefit from, and provide development to, ice sheet-climate coupled model improvements (including UKESM) undertaken in the H2020 project ESM2025 via WP2 co-lead N. Jourdain and WP3 co-lead G. Durand. WP9 UKRI-BAS is a WP co-lead in ARCTIC PASSION and provides a link between the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON) and the OCEAN:ICE analysis of Greenland Ice Sheet stability (WP5/6). WP2 and WP6 of OCEAN:ICE will make significant developmental contributions to core European community modelling efforts NEMO and UKESM and partner closely with these consortia. Links to ecosystem research is provided through collaboration with UK BIOPOLE (A. Meijers, M. Meredith). OCEAN:ICE member EPB leads policy and communications work in SO-CHIC and INTERACT III and legacy planning and implementation in EU-PolarNet 2 and its planned European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO). It will ensure impactful connections and collaborations are made with these and other EU Polar Cluster members.

Clear collaborative opportunities have been identified: Combined AMOC assessment at the SAMBA array (e.g. EPOC WP1, WP5 member S. Speich is a member of AMOC-ASAP); Greenland Ice Sheet and southern freshwater pathways (WP1/5 member A. Naveira Garabato is WP3 lead of AMOC-NEXT); reconstruction of the recent past AMOC water masses (WP5 co-lead E. McDonagh is a member of AMOC-NEXT) and WP5-6 identification of AMOC response to freshwater forcing aligns with EPOC WP4 OCEAN:ICE directly contributes instrumentation and scientific collaboration to the SAMBA project (WP5, S. Speich) through the Brazilian SAMBAR project/Vema channel array (partner E. Campos) and South African DFFE (partner T. Lamont). Data will be collaborated on with the SAMOC project (partner A. Piola) and contribute to the AtlantOS, AANCHOR and the implementation of the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance. It also links to the RAPID array, TRIATLAS and ABC fluxes Atlantic projects via E. McDonagh (WP5 co-lead). Moreover a strong scientific network is established with South Korea KOPRI (partner W. Sang) for deployments of WP2 AUV and WP1 moorings/floats; New Zealand NIWA (partner C. Stevens) for Ross Sea moorings/floats (WP1); Australian AAPP (partner N. Bindoff) for Denman Glacier float deployments (WP1); Japanese JARE/HEAT-CROSS (partner S. Aoki) for Totten glacier float deployments (WP1); German GEOMAR (partner M. Gutjahr) east Antarctic/Amery ice shelf float deployments (WP1), with floats potentially sourced from German BSH (partner B. Klein); Norway NPI (partner/WP1 member T. Hattermann) hot water drilling and borehole access on Fimbul Ice Shelf (WP2) and the South African DFFE (partner T. Lamont) supporting deployment of South Sandwich Trench moorings (WP5). Scientific collaboration and data sharing will be conducted with all partners.

OCEAN:ICE will contribute to the UN Decade on Ocean Science, through EPB's membership of the Task Group leading the process, and chair roles in working groups (R. Badhe, S. Speich), the Southern Ocean Observing System through steering committee or working groups (A. Meijers, J-B. Sallee, M. Janout, P. Dutrioux, M. Meredith), GOOS and associated GO-SHIP initiative, through steering committees (E. McDonagh), ITGC and the NECKLACE programme, through A. Wåhlin and K. Nicholls.

Reduced uncertainties in polar impacts on global climate, including SLR: A core objective of OCEAN:ICE is to reduce the uncertainty in future projections of SLR and climate impacts due to changes in the Antarctic and Greenland Ice Sheets. WP5-6 will produce these results and they will be expected to inform and be cited within IPCC and WOA Assessment Reports and as such influence the UNFCCC processes. These will largely be via the reports/chapters dealing with the cryosphere, oceans, climate/SLR and adaptation. This expectation is supported by the prominent role as co-ordinating lead, lead and contributing authors that numerous OCEAN:ICE members have played in these chapters in previous assessment reports, including the most recent AR6 and the Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate. Additional exploitation of results will be achieved through scientific and steering contributions to the premier model intercomparison projects (CMIP, ISMIP6/7, MISOMIP2) that underpin future projections and uncertainty

Direct improvements to key European and global community ESMs: OCEAN:ICE will improve and further develop several important community ice sheet, oceans and climate models. Improvements to the NEMO ice sheet, sea-ice and isotope modules (WP2) will be adopted into the model 'trunk', providing long term support and integration into future developments. This ocean model forms the basis for several EU coupled climate models, including UKESM that WP5 and WP6 will use to validate the improvements in coupled setups. The focus within OCEAN:ICE on coupling between the wider climate and ice sheets is also recognised as a critically needed next step in climate model development, so community interest and uptake of OCEAN:ICE model development and results is expected to be high. Advances in glacial freshwater integration in NorESM (WP5) will benefit the planned future development of a fully coupled ice sheet-NorESM. Finally, NEMO and other models employed (BISICLES, f.ETISH and Elmer/Ice etc.) are open source and form the basis for many coupled ice sheet-ocean and ESMs globally. Thus it is expected that project model development will propagate far beyond the OCEAN:ICE community.

Support of key operational and reanalysis data products: OCEAN:ICE targets critical gaps in our observational network of the ocean, particularly around the ice threatened Antarctic coastline, under ice shelves and icebergs and in the deep ocean abyss. These data (WP1-3/5) will be quality controlled, processed and propagated (WP7) in delayed mode to the European open access repositories (e.g. CMEMS, EMODnet) responsible for providing data to the historical reconstructions (reanalysis) datasets (e.g. ERA-Interim) and climatologies (EN4). Instruments providing near real time data (e.g. floats deployed for the German Argo initiative) will also provide information in these data deserts to support operational weather and sea-ice forecasting models (e.g. from ECMWF) that feed through to services such as the Copernicus Maritime Surveillance Service that support operations from fisheries to maritime safety.

Improved coordination between ocean and ice modelling, observational and EO communities: OCEAN:ICE recognises the need for greater coordination between the polar in situ, EO and modelling communities to tackle the deeply coupled problem of polar impacts on climate.

Coordination and dissemination of observations from new and emerging technologies: OCEAN:ICE exploits novel and emerging polar observing platforms, such as ice-avoiding profiling floats in bottom landing mode, AUV instrumentation, experimental isotope and mixing instrumentation deployed through ice boreholes and ice penetrating radar (ApRES). There is a recognised need to bring together these disparate datasets, often only held by individual research teams, into more integrated data delivery platforms. In collaboration with OCEAN:ICE (WP7,8), SOOS will coordinate a workshop (2024/2025) on the standardisation, harmonisation and sharing of such datasets.

Improved long term monitoring capability: While most OCEAN:ICE observations are derived from short term instrument deployments, the WP5 instrumentation of the SAMBA array and establishment of a deep mooring array at the South Sandwich Trench reflect a commitment to the long-term monitoring of AABW pathways and properties. These instruments will remain in place, maintained by the SAMBA array consortium and UKRI-BAS respectively, beyond the lifetime of OCEAN:ICE. They will provide an OCEAN:ICE legacy to continue monitoring the multi-decadal decline in AABW volume as it spreads north to form part of the lower overturning cell in the AMOC.

4 FAIR data

Since 1960, the IODE has been publishing manuals and guides¹⁰ that dealt with operational procedures for data collection, quality assessment and quality control, standards and reference materials, data formats, etc. Harmonisation of marine in situ data is necessary for scientists of different disciplines and experts in various fields to share information and tackle together a specific marine phenomenon or threat.

Marine observations generate raw data which can be stored in repositories commonly known as data archive centres (DACs). DACs give access to datasets, metadata and sometimes data-products. With dozens of expert DACs, the OCEAN:ICE marine data landscape is diverse and complex. Public marine data are accessed via many different routes.

Over the last three decades great progress was made at European level in terms of advancing these standards and facilitating machine-to-machine data processing, and programs and projects such as Copernicus, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, H2020 EuroSea etc are continuously updating these recommendations (see Tanhua et al. 2019 for an exhaustive review). These recommendations are made according to the FAIR principles broken down into the 15 characteristics laid down by the FORCE11¹¹ collective and clearly described in Quimbert et al. (2022).

¹⁰ https://www.iode.org/index.php?option=com_oe&task=viewDoclistRecord&doclistID=9

¹¹ <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

FORCE11 is a community of scholars, librarians, archivists, publishers and research funders that has arisen organically to help facilitate the change toward improved knowledge creation and sharing.

Table 2. FAIR principles proposed by the FORCE11 community

Findable	
F1	(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.
F2	data are described with rich metadata.
F3	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
F4	metadata specify the data identifier.
Accessible	
A1	(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
A1.1	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
A1.2	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
A2	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.
Interoperable	
I1	(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
I3	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.
Re-usable	
R1	(meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
R1.1	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
R1.2	(meta)data are associated with their provenance.
R1.3	(meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

Notably, these recommendations are always including three main elements for implementing the interoperability, namely metadata (including data quality), data format and data services.

More specifically, according to our Grant Agreement (Art.187), metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular, machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following:

- publication (author(s),
- title,
- date of publication,
- publication venue,
- Horizon Europe or Euratom funding,
- grant project name, acronym and number,
- licensing terms,
- persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.

Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

When

The partners will have to make their research data available as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensuring open access.

Nevertheless, data usability strongly depends on the data policy license and in such regard, there is an increasing push for adopting the Common Creative framework and in particular the CC-BY license (the

only limitation is that credit must be given to creator). Embargo of data and other CC-license can also be applied wherever the policy is 'As open as possible as closed as necessary'.

Partners can avoid offering open access in two cases:

- OA be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation,

or

- OA be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP.

4.2 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

4.2.1 Observational platform

Each in situ platform/station should be identified by a unique ID. A WMO code is assigned (OceanOPS, <https://www.ocean-ops.org/>) to ARGO, drifting buoy, mooring buoy, fixed ocean platform (e.g. SAMBA array), autonomous vehicle.

4.2.2 Institution

The institution responsible (operating) for the marine in situ data should be displayed. This should be done through an EDMO code that references marine institutions all over the world. The information and any organisation's code can be found on SeaDataNet website¹². Table 3 reports EDMO codes of OCEAN:ICE partners.

Table 3. OCEAN:ICE partners' EDMO code.

Participant organisation	EDMO code	EDMO link
United Kingdom Research and Innovation	4946	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/4946
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	5153	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5153
Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut	469	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/469
Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum Fur Polar-Und Meeresforschung	1368	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1368
Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique	552	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/552
University of Northumbria at Newcastle	5400	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5400
University of Southampton	1801	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1801
Universiteit Utrecht	1627	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1627
ETT SPA	2764	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2764
Université Libre de Bruxelles	717	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/717
Ecole Normale Supérieure	4763	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/4763
Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	3445	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3445
University of Bristol	1475	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1475
University of Gothenburg	3984	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3984
University of Reading	2080	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2080
Norwegian Polar Institute	1349	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1349
European Polar Board	5859	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5859

¹² <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/results>

4.2.3 Principal Investigator and Research Team

Actors associated with the data should be referenced by a persistent digital identifier as for example an ORCID identifier¹³.

4.2.4 Project Identifier and funding

Funding supporting the project should be referenced and CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) is hosting the European Commission's primary source of results from the projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation, from FP1 to Horizon Europe. CORDIS hosts a landing page and a doi for each project.

The OCEAN:ICE reference on CORDIS is: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060452>

Research community is, anyhow, used to search for projects by using complementary DB and the SeaDataNet EDMERP (European Directory of Marine and Environmental Research Project). The code (5 digits) of a project can be found or obtained for a new project on SeaDataNet website¹⁴. The OCEAN:ICE reference on the EDMERP database: <https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/report/13721>.

4.2.5 Dataset Identifier

The datasets should be identified by a DOI, persistent identifier for object and ISO standard. The two main reference DOI publishers in Europe are ZENODO¹⁵ for any research fields (and including data, papers, software ...), SEANOE¹⁶ and PANGAEA¹⁷ for marine research data. The granularity of the dataset, to which a DOI should be assigned, is not homogeneous and not yet consolidated. An important point is that each DOI including the reference to the same dataset (only this one or among others) should be linked together (e.g. a DOI assigned to a platform and a DOI assigned to the network of all the platforms) to allow complete traceability of the initial platform. One major problem when seeking to uniquely identify the data digital objects is the fragmentation of the data acquisition process. If we consider the ARGO as an example, data from each profiler are reviewed and checked against climatological data and nearby Argo data from different profiler. But ARGO are continuously uploading new data (same ARGO with new profiles, new ARGOS) and updates to existing data when delayed mode quality control is done. To overcome this issue, it's important to include and refer to a timestamp and identify the "version" (identify time relative to changes to the dataset).

4.2.6 Workflow to collect DOI and make OCEAN:ICE data available

As anticipated, OCEAN:ICE data products may be near real time, delayed mode or reanalysis (including model output), it applies a simple and effective strategy to assign a DOI and publish/link the products. It works as reported in the following chapters.

¹³ Information and registration: <https://orcid.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata/EDMERP-Projects>

¹⁵ <https://help.zenodo.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.seanoe.org/html/doi-complementarity-with-databases.htm>

¹⁷ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

4.2.6.1 Operational (near real time) data

If the data product is accessible (institute portal, assembly centre...), the PI informs WP7 about the URL/link to access to the source, and WP7 develops the machine-to-machine interoperability between the OCEAN:ICE data portal and the partner data infrastructure.

If the data is not visible/accessible yet, the PI informs WP7 about the availability of new data and WP7 provides the PI with support to either drop (periodically) these data into a virtual folder (e.g. FTP folder) or (preferred) install an ERDDAP instance at the institute infrastructure to enable native interoperability without data transfer.

Where “inform” means: supporting WP7 to collect the necessary metadata for implementing FAIR principles.

4.2.6.2 Delayed mode and reanalysis

The PI collects and processes data according to community best practice and standards, complete data with metadata (see next section). Apply for a DOI by considering (in order of relevance and recommendation) 1) national infrastructure¹⁸, 2) SEANOE + EMODnet Data Ingestion, 3) PANAGEA, 4) Zenodo. Inform WP7 about the DOI/URL where the data are hosted. WP7 will link these data into OCEAN:ICE infrastructure.

Where “link” means: implementing interoperability and avoiding duplicates of data products as much as possible.

4.3 Making data accessible (and use of common vocabularies)

4.3.1 Data Format

Transport format is one of the key elements for implementing data interoperability and having a common transport format is an open community issue. The European marine data infrastructures are based on the format of the files that are used to distribute OceanSITES data model (with some extensions to provide the user with more information). Typically, the transport format for operational data is NetCDF (CF Convention). The NetCDF CF (v1.6 or greater) file format should be preferred as it is commonly used by the marine community and by the data integrators for in situ data as well as for satellite and modelling ones. It is a self-describing format, which eases the understanding of the file content. Another widely used scientific data file format is HDF¹⁹. Both NetCDF and HDF provide compact, binary formats optimised for efficient storage and access of large, complex datasets and support features such as internal compression, and support hierarchical structuring of data within files.

4.3.2 Metadata

The adoption of ISO standards and the use of shared controlled vocabularies are a key prerequisite towards consistency and this data integrator and data mediator role. ISO 19115 Standard²⁰ requires a basic minimum number of metadata elements that are essential for the data presentation:

- Dataset or dataset series on specific challenges (‘what’),

¹⁸ e.g. in France, IFREMER can assign DOI; in Italy, INGV; in Germany, PANAGEA, etc.

¹⁹ <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

²⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

- Geographic bounding box ('where'),
- Temporal extent ('when'),
- Contact point to learn more about or order the dataset ('who').

The key references for cataloguing the information used in OCEAN:ICE are:

- ISO 8601 Representation of date and time,
- SeaDataNet NVS P0x description of parameters,
- Climate and Forecasting conventions for parameters standard names,
- WGS84 for Datum,
- links to the processing history of the observations (i.e., source, version, quality assessment and control, sensors).

Table 4. Metadata Vocabularies

Metadata field	Vocabulary exists	Link to vocabulary	Vocabulary governance	Mandatory / Suggested
Platform id		https://www.ocean-ops.org/	OCEANOPS – WMO	M
Platform type	Yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/	BODC	M
sensor_model	Yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22/current/ Sensor URL	BODC -NVS	S
contributors_role				
naming_authority	Yes	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/	SeaDataNet	M
Institution	Yes	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/	SeaDataNet	M
qc_method	*	doi		M
Group parameters	yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P02/current/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P33/current/	BODC – EMODnet Physics	M
variable names	Yes	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/	BODC – NVS	S S M
unit	Yes	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/	SeaDataNet	M
Quality Flag Scheme	Yes	https://vocab.seadatanet.org/v_bodc_vocab_v2/search.asp?lib=L20	SeaDataNet	M
Time	Yes	ISO8601	ISO	M
Datum	Yes	WGS84	ISO	M
Country	Yes	ISO3166	ISO	M
Licence	Yes	https://creativecommons.org/	CC	M
INSPIRE	Yes	ISO 19115	ISO/INSPIRE	M
PI	Yes	https://orcid.org/	ORCID	S
data_doi				S
Project_ID	Yes	https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/	SeaDataNet	M
funding_ID		https://cordis.europa.eu/	CORDIS	
funding_statement				S

Table 5. Parameters Vocabularies

ID	Title	Description	Governance	New terms request - link
P01	BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary	Terms built using the BODC parameter semantic model designed to describe individual measured phenomena. May be used to mark up sets of data such as a NetCDF array or spreadsheet column. Units must be specified when using a P01 code. The P06 unit that is linked to individual P01 in the NVS is the one used in BODC's systems but external users can use any appropriate units.	British Oceanographic Data Centre	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/ https://github.com/nvs-vocabs/P01
P02	SeaDataNet Parameter Discovery Vocabulary	Terms describing fine-grained related groups of measurement phenomena designed to be used in dataset discovery interfaces.	SeaDataNet	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P02/current/ https://github.com/nvs-vocabs/P02
P09	MEDATLAS Parameter Usage Vocabulary	Terms under the content governance of SISMER used to describe measured phenomena within the MEDATLAS project.	Systèmes d'Informations Scientifiques pour la Mer	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/
P06	BODC approved data storage units	Terms approved for use by BODC to describe the measurement units for data held in its repositories.	British Oceanographic Data Centre	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/ https://github.com/nvs-vocabs/P06
R03	Argo parameter codes	Terms describing individual measured phenomena, used to mark-up sets of data in Argo netCDF arrays. Argo netCDF variables PARAMETER and TRAJECTORY_PARAMETERS are populated by R03 altLabel; R03 altLabel is also used to name netCDF profile files parameter variables <PARAMETER>.	Argo Data Management Team	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R03/current/
OG1	OceanGliders Parameter Usage Vocabulary	Terms in this vocabulary are under the content governance of the OceanGliders Data Management Task Team (OGDMTT) on behalf of the OceanGliders community and Everyone's Gliding Observatories (EGO). Terms describe measured phenomena within the OG/EGO format.	OceanGliders Data Management Task Team	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/OG1/current/ https://github.com/nvs-vocabs/R03

The tables and will be updated continuously as soon as needed.

4.3.3 Use of uncommon or unavailable ontologies or vocabularies

The NVS offers both NVS RESTful, SOAP and SPARQL services. A GitHub repository for key NVS vocabularies²¹ tracks the discussion on new terms adoption. OCEAN:ICE partners are already using these services and are collaborating with SeaDataNet and linked projects (e.g., EMODnet).

The NVS service is also open to map and manage new terms and ontologies, therefore the primary approach of OCEAN:ICE will be to interact with the service (and the people managing the vocabulary) to have a community definition, acceptance and hence adoption of new proposed terms.

4.3.4 INSPIRE

The INSPIRE Directive aims to create a European Union spatial data infrastructure for the purposes of EU environmental policies and policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment. This European spatial data infrastructure will enable the sharing of environmental spatial information

²¹ github.com/nvs-vocabs

among public sector organisations, facilitate public access to spatial information across Europe and assist in policy making across boundaries. INSPIRE is based on the infrastructures for spatial information established and operated by the Member States of the European Union. The directive addresses 34 spatial data themes needed for environmental applications. The directive is defined in a generic manner, providing overall requirements towards metadata and data provision, together with a short description of the data themes encompassed. Based on the framework defined within the directive, implementing rules have been formulated detailing explicit requirements that must be adopted by the Member States. In addition, technical guidelines have been developed that help Member States to comply with these implementing rules. As an example in EMODnet, it has been adopted GeoNetwork as the integrating catalogue that offers INSPIRE discovery features.

4.3.4.1 Compliance requirements

INSPIRE requires that the data being made available for specific INSPIRE themes includes all concepts specified within the data specifications for the relevant themes, and laid down in the Commission Regulation regarding the interoperability of spatial data sets and services (1253/2013/EU). That document formalises which spatial objects are to be made available for a specific theme, together with which attributes are to be provided for each spatial object type. In order to facilitate the provision and sharing of data falling under INSPIRE, the data specifications have been designed in UML, which was subsequently transformed into XML Schema documents (XSD) made available by the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) at <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/schemas/>. Whilst providing data falling under INSPIRE in accordance with the XSDs is not mandatory, this is recommended to allow for better interoperability of data stemming from different sources.

4.3.4.2 Relevant INSPIRE themes

Based on the preliminary analysis of data to be administered by the system, the data specifications for the INSPIRE Themes Environmental Monitoring Facilities and Oceanographic Geographical Features apply. The INSPIRE Themes Environmental Monitoring Facilities (EF) is comprised of the following feature types:

- Environmental Monitoring Activity,
- Environmental Monitoring Facility,
- Environmental Monitoring Network,
- Environmental Monitoring Programme,
- Observing Capability,
- Operational Activity Period.

In addition, observational data are to be provided in accordance with the observational model from the Generic Conceptual Model (GCM) and specified in the INSPIRE deliverable D2.9 Guidelines for the use of Observations & Measurements and Sensor Web Enablement-related standards in INSPIRE. This model is extended from the Observations and Measurements (O&M) data model formalised in ISO 19156, providing specialised feature types as required for various types of observational or measurement data falling under INSPIRE. Of specific relevance are the specialised observation types, defined for the provision of various types of observational data; the specialisation pertains to various constraints on the observation such as the type of object being measured or the type of result to be provided:

- pointObservation,
- pointTimeSeriesObservation,
- multiPointObservation,
- profileObservation,
- trajectoryObservation,
- gridObservation,
- gridSeriesObservation.

Within the INSPIRE Theme Oceanographic Geographical Features (OF), the specification is devolved to various packages stemming from the observational model, including:

- Specialised Observations,
- Processes,
- Observable Properties,
- Observation References.

4.3.4.3 OF, EF, O&M data models

As shown in the section above, there are strong interlinkages between the INSPIRE Themes OF, EF as well as the Observational Model from the GCM. The OF Theme specifies which of the specialised observation types are to be utilised. The EF Theme specifies how the facilities (various platform types, i.e. vessels, buoys, etc.) are to be described. The Observational Model describes the various specialised observation types as well as the feature types to be utilised for the provision of information on the measurement process as well as the properties being observed. Within the Oceanographic Geographical Features data specification, in addition to mentioning the relevance of the coupled environmental monitoring facilities for the provision of information on the process used to derive the data on physical conditions, the INSPIRE Theme Sea Regions (SR) is considered to be of importance, as these provide the spatial context of OF feature.

4.4 Making data Interoperable

4.4.1 Data Services

To facilitate the data harmonisation and operate as integrator and data translator for facilitating the data use and interoperability it is important to use common open tools to query for and view data collections and data products. The GOOS Observation Coordination Group (OCG), coordinating the activities of the global ocean observing networks, is working to improve data interoperability between and within the various observing networks. The OCG is actively promoting the use of ERDDAP²² as a key tool towards interoperability of global ocean datasets. ERDDAP data server is open-source software written in Java that builds upon the open-source ideals of the OPeNDAP, WCS, SOS and OBIS standards. ERDDAP data server supports several common data file formats (html table, netcdf, csv, txt, mat, json, etc.) and output files are created on the fly in any of this format. ERDDAP implements FGDC Web Accessible Folder (WAF) with FGDC-STD-001-1998 and ISO 19115 WAF with ISO 19115-2/19139. Another tool that is increasing in popularity and use is GeoNetwork. GeoNetwork, based on an open source (GNOS) project, is a free and open source (FOSS) cataloguing application for spatially referenced resources. GeoNetwork provides a web interface to search geospatial data across multiple catalogues. The search provides full-text search as well as faceted search on keywords, resource types, organisations, scale, etc. The catalogue is able to describe geospatial layers, services, maps and also non geographic datasets. GeoNetwork implements WxS, OGC, ISO 19115/119/110 standards used for spatial resources and also the Dublin Core format usually used for open data portals. OCEAN:ICE is adopting data interoperability infrastructure that is based on ERDDAP, GeoNetwork and GeoServer (to manage vectorial data and map layers). These services allow metadata to be harvested and indexed.

4.4.2 OCEAN:ICE data infrastructure

The current OCEAN:ICE backend design considers 2 VMs: 2.10GHz - 4 Core, 32GB, running CentOS and 500GB of allocated disk size. The VMs are running Docker containers. Containers are similar to VMs, but they have relaxed isolation properties to share the Operating System (OS) amongst the applications. Similar to a VM, a container has its own file system, share of CPU, memory, process space, and more. As they are decoupled from the underlying infrastructure, they are portable across clouds and OS distributions. The most popular solutions are Kubernetes and Docker that have become the de- facto standard and dominant tool with which applications are containerized, managed, scaled and released. As anticipated, OCEAN:ICE adopted Docker that offers packages with service tools like selected data publishing services.

²² <https://coastwatch.pfeg.noaa.gov/erddap/index.html>

Figure 10. Deployed architecture

As shown in Figure 10, the management of the access to the private area is implemented by using a selective endpoint access from a given (white) list of IP address or host and domain name (fully qualified domain name, FQDN). Connections and access from edge devices out of the list will be rejected. The idea to design a delivery buffer is mutated from the CMEMS Dissemination Unit (DU)²³ Delivery buffer. Similarly, the OCEAN:ICE Delivery buffer provides the partners with virtual folders in which new data can be dropped. As described in the OCEAN:ICE DMP, a preliminary approach suggests the partners to use an internal naming convention for new datasets. This facilitates the successive ingestion step that pushes new data into the OCEAN:ICE database and the data publication tools.

As anticipated, OCEAN:ICE data publishing identified tools are ERDDAP and GeoServer, which are tools for both the OCEAN:ICE service layer (they offer application program interfaces and machine-to-machine services for internal use) and the OCEAN:ICE application layer (they offer cataloguing features and machine-to-machine tools for external users).

4.4.3 Delivering data to (trusted) infrastructure

Marine data landscape is diverse and complex. In the European landscape, leading European marine data management infrastructures (such as Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet, Euro-Argo and Argo GDAC, ICOS-Marine, SeaDataNet, etc) provide services for discovery and access to collected marine in-situ and remote sensing data and for ensuring long-term stewardship. Project partners are involved in or are working with these systems and infrastructures and arrangements are already in place.

Lately, these infrastructures are also connected to EOSC (see e.g. <https://blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures>), hence ensuring an easy and automatic flow of new data (and data products) towards trusted (and EOSC) infrastructures.

²³ The CMEMS DU is in charge of the dissemination of the products elaborated by Production Centres (PC; MFCs and TACs), and provide the users with available products by means of several dissemination interfaces. The CMEMS DU is also in charge for monitoring overall system performances (timeliness, availability, bandwidth load, etc.).

4.5 Making data Reusable/Increase data re-use

4.5.1 Data Quality Principles

The principles aim to encourage all involved in research to maintain, and to respond adequately to possible threats or violations of research integrity. OCEAN:ICE researchers should be guided by these principles at each stage of the project work and in particular they have to ensure:

4.5.1.1 Academic Excellence

Researchers have to apply sound methodology, suitable methods, standard procedures and documented protocols where appropriate, to ensure the highest quality of work, its dissemination and replicability.

4.5.1.2 Honesty

Researchers must acknowledge the direct and indirect contributions of colleagues, collaborators and others. The basic principle of any scientific activity is the need for researchers to be honest in respect of their own actions and in their responses to the actions of other scientists.

4.5.1.3 Accountability

Researchers should recognise their responsibility to the general public, and should take all reasonable measures to ensure that their research complies with any agreement, related policies and professional bodies' guidance; and allows for proper governance and transparency.

4.5.1.4 Care and Respect

Researchers should avoid any unreasonable risk or harm to research subjects and researchers themselves.

4.5.2 Data Quality

The platform data.europa.eu (i.e. the official portal for European Union (EU) data) has recently published the data quality guidelines for delivering high-quality open data. These recommendations are directed at data providers to support them in preparing their data, developing their data strategy and ensuring data quality. OCEAN:ICE is adopting these recommendations and in particular is applying measures for making data FAIR, using well known and standardized data models and formats, adopting backend data infrastructures that supports multi-formats manipulation and conversion, using common vocabularies and standards (ISO and community defined dictionaries), adopting easy data access and data download tools. Moreover each data collected and produced in OCEAN:ICE will refer/document the applied (scientific) methodology (citation of references).

Quality control procedures depend upon the type of platform, OCEAN:ICE will include links to applied procedures (best practices) in the metadata.

4.5.3 Data Description and documentation (including codebooks)

In 2021, OECD revised its Recommendation concerning Access to Research Data from Public Funding to cover not only research data, but also related metadata (data about data, specifying their sources, methodology and limitations), as well as the bespoke algorithms, workflows, models and software (including code) that are essential for their interpretation. According to OECD, this may contribute to further enhancing access to and sharing of marine data.

4.5.4 Data Traceability

In all aspects of research, substantive contributions of formal collaborators and all others who directly assist or indirectly support the research must be properly acknowledged. This applies to any circumstances in which statements about the research are made, including provision of information about the nature and process of the research, and in publishing the outcome. Failure to acknowledge the contributions of others is regarded as unethical conduct. OCEAN:ICE is adopting all necessary measure to ensure data traceability. This applies to data and data products that are going to be (re)used in the project and is achieved by documenting the sources and the methods (references, DOI, or any other identifier whenever available/applicable). It also applies data products that are collected and produced by OCEAN:ICE by properly documenting and by assigning a DOI to each of them.

4.5.5 Data License

OCEAN:ICE is an EU supported research project, hence all the collected data have to be freely available to the community at no cost and limitation. Simply ensuring that data are freely and openly available is not enough to effectively improve data interoperability, though of course this is necessary. As anticipated, data license is key element for interoperability and it should consider the following:

- When possible, to give open and free access to the data. Note that this access can be done through authorisation or authentication if needed.
- To provide to the data actor (creator) a standardised way to grant permission to use his/her work done under copyright law.
- To be clear and accessible to the user or data actor and readable by a machine.

The licence “Creative Commons” (CC²⁴) gathers these characteristics. It lists 6 different licence types from most to least permissive with the common point that credits must be given to the creator. The most permissive: CC-BY (with the only limitation that credit must be given to creator)²⁵ should be preferred, following the principle ‘as open as possible as closed as necessary’.

An Embargo period may also be applied. The Embargo is the period during which access to the dataset is temporarily restricted. Usually, embargoes are applied while researchers are awaiting publication or pursuing a patent. Typical embargo periods range from 6 to 24 months from the data collection time. In any case metadata will be open under CC 0 or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles and provide information about the licensing terms and persistent identifiers, amongst others.

²⁴ Refer to <https://creativecommons.org/about/cclicenses/> for all detailed information on CC licences.

²⁵ CC BY-NC/CC BY-ND are allowed for long-text formats

4.5.6 Planned measurements

Table 6. Mooring.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)
M9 Deployment of moorings in South Sandwich Trench	UKRI-BAS	30/04/2023 (6M)
M4 Instrument deployment through Fimbul Ice Shelf borehole	UKRI-BAS	31/12/2023 (14M)
M2 Deployment of various moored instruments	AWI	31/10/2024 (24M)
M10 Recovery of moorings in South Sandwich Trench	UKRI-BAS	30/04/2025 (30M)
D1.6 Deployment of bottom pressure recorders	UKRI-BAS	30/09/2025 (36M)
D2.4 Observations of the ocean beneath Fimbul Ice Shelf	UKRI-BAS	30/09/2025 (36M)

Table 7. AUV.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)
M3 Deployment of AUV in the Amundsen Sea	UGOT	31/12/2023 (14M)
D2.2 AUV observations under the sea-ice around grounded icebergs	UGOT	31/10/2024 (24M)
D2.3 Ship and AUV observations near /within a warm ice-shelf cavity	UGOT	31/10/2024 (24M)

Table 8. Argo.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)
M1 Deployment of 3 pairs of Argo floats	UKRI-BAS	31/10/2024 (24M)
D1.5 Deployment of profiling floats as pairs	UKRI-BAS	31/03/2026 (42M)

Table 9. Drifting buoys.

Activity	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)
Polarstern cruise to East Antarctic, the Amery Ice Shelf, at the end of the year 2023 - floats to be sent along	AWI	31/03/2026 (42M)
Floats on the cruise from Japan with international collaborator Shigeru Aoki (Aoki's project)	UKRI-BAS	31/03/2026 (42M)
Floats in either Amundsen or eastern Ross Sea	UKRI-BAS	31/03/2026 (42M)

5 Impact

5.1 Contribution to the project objectives

The OCEAN:ICE DMP is setting the schemes and rules for project data management and sharing. More specifically is pillar for the implementation of the:

O7: Deliver free and open data access and contribute to international assessments, climate model development, observing initiatives and policymakers.

As described in the previous section, OCEAN:ICE is setting up a data management infrastructure that is adopting and adapting the recommendations and lesson learnt from major European Marine Data initiatives and interoperable towards both EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service. It applies FAIR principles and implements tools to be INSPIRE compliant. OCEAN:ICE is also supporting the further development and empowerment of the *SOOSmap* data system.

5.2 Contribution to the Expected Outcomes

The DMP is supporting the OCEAN:ICE data management towards all its EOs.

5.3 Policy relevance

OCEAN:ICE Data Management Plan is setting (proposing) a better and clearer schema for data delivery and Commission assessment on the Horizon Europe project data FAIRness, more specifically is embracing and promoting the adoption of CC and in particularly CC-BY whenever possible, and it is proposing to have clear statements on embargoed data, meaning that some data will may go under embargo for enabling scientific processing and fine tuning (and publication) but since now the project is declaring that all the data will be available and linkable. New data (observational capacity) is already declared and at the end of the project it can be easily tracked if and how much the project was compliant to this statement.

Being in contact – cooperating with the major European Marine Data Integrators (EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service) is important to have a further channel to make value of the project data. Some OCEAN:ICE data may be not included in these integrators (because of the scope, type ...) but it is important that the once that are of interest of those initiative can easily flow to/interoperate with them. The adoption of open data sharing tools (e.g. ERDDAP) are further cornerstones of this process and should be encouraged as a EU policy for research projects.

6 Other research outputs

OCEAN:ICE is an ambitious project and there will be several outputs going from new data and products to deliverables, to publications, to dissemination materials. These outputs are planned and this approach matches the open science practices. This document is describing the approach on data and data-products data management approach, while plans for communication strategy, deliverable quality, document management, web and social communication are addressed in other deliverables. The reader can refer to the Project Handbook (MS28) for an easy guide/index towards all these deliverables.

The project' data and data-products are digital objects and they will be published together with (FAIR) metadata, be assigned a digital object identifier (doi) and be available/linkable in the OCEAN:ICE web portal or web data infrastructure.

When applicable, these digital object will be also included in the OCEAN:ICE ZENODO community - <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=oceanice>

7 Allocation of Resources

7.1 Costs before making data or other research outputs FAIR

Besides the development and hosting of the data infrastructure that enables the compliance with FAIR principles, mainly allocated by the partner ETT, all the partners have allocated a dedicated budget for the promotion and dissemination activities.

7.2 Responsible for data management

Data Management is included in a dedicated project work package (WP7) and responsible for the data management is Antonio Novellino, who has long experience in data management and ocean data management and sharing. Following is his employment history in brief.

He holds a PhD in Biotechnology and Bioengineering, MSc Biomedical Engineering, and is Research Manager at ETT. From 2008 to 2010, he served the European Commission, JRC – IHCP as a senior researcher. He works in ETT (R&D in Smart and sustainable cities). He serves on the scientific board of the Ligurian Cluster of Marine Technology DLTM (www.dltm.it) and the board of Consortium TRAIN. He is member of the EuroGOOS DATAMEQ group and contributes to several EuroGOOS Task Teams for advising (<http://eurogoos.eu/>) on operational oceanography data management procedures and standards. He is member of the SOOS DMSC (South Ocean Observing System Data Management Steering Committee) and DOOS DMTT (Deep Ocean Observing System Data Management Technical Team). He serves on the EMODnet Steering Committee, the EMODnet Technical Working Group. He serves the Expert Team on WIS Centres (ET-WISC) and Task Team on Data Centres (TT-DC). He is co-author of scientific publications and he participates as reviewer for scientific journals for Elsevier and Frontiers. He is the EGU ESSI 1.1/OS4.35 session main convener. He is the EMODnet Physics coordinator and CMEMS DU deputy coordinator. He is deeply involved in EMODnet Data Ingestion and in the EMOD-PACE Partnership for China-Europe project, and major EU projects in the field of oceanography and marine data management (SCHeMA project on FP7 Ocean of Tomorrow; JERICONEXT on H2020; AtlantOS on H2020 BG8, SeaDataCloud on H2020, EuroSEA on H2020, Jerico S3 on H2020, SO-CHIC on H2020, NAUTILOS on H2020, EMODnet Baltic Sea Check Point on EMFF/EASME, INCREASE CMEMS Service Evolution on CMEMS, LAMBDA CMEMS Service Evolution on CMEMS).

Whenever an OCEAN:ICE data product is hosted, safe kept into any other well-known/TRUST repository, WP7 will list the proper links.

7.3 Long term preservation

For the duration of the project, data is going to be hosted by the OCEAN:ICE data management infrastructure. This infrastructure is going to be interoperable with the key European integrating data

ocean infrastructures and programs (CMEMS, EMODnet and SeaDataCloud) and new data will directly be harvested by these long-term safe keeping systems. It should be noted that EMODnet and in particular by means of the EMODnet Data Ingestion and Safe Keeping project, is implementing a dedicated action to collect and provide long-term preservation of ocean data and OCEAN:ICE DMP is considering also this system as a possible system for its data legacy.

OCEAN:ICE backend infrastructure will be maintained for at least 3 years after the end of the project (longer time will be considered if there will be any specific need).

8 Data Security

The infrastructure is going to be deployed on the ARUBA.it infrastructure²⁶. Since 2015 Aruba is running a dedicated service to private business clients and it provides the client with top level services such as Data Centre (Virtual Servers, Real Servers, hosting infrastructures), Back up and Disaster Recovery etc. ARUBA also provides us with most recent services for data security cryptography (AES), security protocols (AES, SSL) and bandwidth balance. The main characteristics of the service are:

SLA:	99,80%
Security:	crypted transmission channel (optional) storage crypting AES-256
Min backup timing:	1h
Schedule:	anytime granularity – single backup job
Backup Account number:	unlimited
Concurrent agents:	depends on the agreed service
Max number of backup jobs:	unlimited
Bandwidth:	unlimited (upload/download)
Certifications:	ISO 9001:2015, ISO 27001:2013
Service desk:	24h
Cloud security certification:	ISO/IEC 27017:2015
Data privacy:	ISO/IEC 2018:2014
Security incidents:	ISO/IEC 27035:2016

9 Ethics and GDPR

Ethics and GDPR are covered by the OCEAN:ICE Project Handbook (Milestone M28) and the deliverable D9.9 “OCEAN:ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy (EDI)”.

10 Conclusions

This document presented the preliminary version of the OCEAN:ICE Data Management Plan (DMP) and it is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) template. OCEAN:ICE moves beyond

²⁶ <https://business.aruba.it/azienda.aspx>

open access in implementing open science practices while following Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles.

It applies to research data collected during the project as well as to publications.

All observational data and derived products will be made freely available via EU public data repositories and a data management backend will be implemented (WP7) that provides immediate and free access to collected data. Besides adopting open data management software tools (e.g. ERDDAP, GeoServer, GeoNetwork), and supporting INSPIRE themes (e.g. European harmonised and controlled vocabularies), OCEAN:ICE contributes to the development of needed extensions and will share these outcomes via open repositories (e.g. GitHub, StackOverflow) as well as provides docker images of deployed and configured tools. Project developed data management software tools will be made freely available under creative commons/open data commons licencing.

11 Updates of the DMP

This DMP will be updated in months 36.

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